

Microwave Properties of Screen Printed Carbon Nanotubes Thick Film

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Abstract

Carbon nanotubes have been received more attention due to their excellent electrical properties and lightweight nature. For their use in the microwave frequency region, these MWCNTs are transformed into planar form. In the present study, the properties of MWCNTs thick film on alumina substrate has been reported for the first time by the screen printing method. The functionalization process of MWCNT with acid solution resulted into the reduction in agglomeration and surface modification of CNTs with carboxylic groups. The thickness obtained for the present MWCNT thick film is around 10 μm . The MWCNT were thermally stable in nitrogen atmosphere up to 750 $^{\circ}\text{C}$. The X-ray diffraction pattern of MWCNT thick film shows two characteristic graphitic peaks at 26.5 $^{\circ}$ and 54.7 $^{\circ}$ corresponding to (002) and (004) reflections. The real and imaginary microwave permittivity of MWCNT thick film from the straight resonator overlay method were 6.6 and 17.6 respectively

Keywords – Multiwalled carbon nanotubes, Screen printing, Thick film, Microwave permittivity